

DEVELOPMENT OF A STRUCTURAL OPTIMISATION METHODOLOGY FOR USE IN THE DESIGN OF A COMPOSITE SEMI-TRAILER CHASSIS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates options for lightweighting a 13.5 m long flat-bed road trailer chassis through the application of composites and structural optimisation. Trailer load cases are first understood through finite element modelling in Abaqus. A parametric model of a typical 13.5 m trailer built from steel I-beam was developed, using Python scripting and the finite element package Abaqus. The model has been used to show that the conventional steel I-beams could be reduced in weight by 28% (140 kg). The model has been expanded to analyse composite trailer structures. It showed that approximately 1,300 kg of weight could be saved by shape and material optimisation in a composite trailer, while mechanical performance is maintained to an acceptable level and increases in raw material costs are minimised.

1 INTRODUCTION

In road haulage the empty weight of a vehicle is a significant contributor to fuel consumption and resulting CO₂ emissions. The application of lightweight materials in semi-trailer design is one avenue that needs to be explored in reducing the carbon footprint of road freight vehicles. There are very few regulations which determine the structural design of typical road freight trailers, providing large scope for innovation in design. Composite trailers can combine both aerodynamic and structural functions, leading to significantly reduced weight with improved performance.

The aim of this paper is to investigate the potential design space into which a holistic composite trailer could fit, to give future lightweighting projects a better understanding as to the limits of weight reduction that can be achieved with composite materials. This is achieved through finite element modelling in conjunction with shape and material optimisation of a hypothetical composite trailer.

2 REVIEW OF THE CRITICAL CHASSIS LOAD CASE

A robust lightweight redesign of a trailer chassis requires sound understanding of the in-service loadings. The critical load case (Fig. 1), of a fully loaded trailer parked resting on its landing legs and the trailer bogie, was identified with the help of industrial partners. A 30 tonne uniform distributed load (UDL) represents a fully loaded trailer, estimated using the following considerations:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Payload} &= \text{Maximum Combination Weight} - \text{Tractor Tare Weight} - \text{Trailer Tare Weight} \\ \text{Payload} &= 44,000 - 7,500 - 6,500 = 30,000 \text{ kg}\end{aligned}$$

This critical load case was investigated through a linear-elastic finite element analysis of a conventional 13.5 m steel chassis performed in Abaqus. The CAD model used in the analysis is a simplified version of a CAD model provided by an industrial partner. The boundary conditions corresponding to the critical load case are also shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: The most critical load case (resting on landing legs and trailer) and its corresponding boundary conditions (courtesy of SDC Trailers).

In terms of design constraints, a safety factor of two is typically applied to account for dynamic loading and fatigue. Hence the maximum allowable stresses are generally set to half the yield stress of the high-strength low-alloy steel (YS355) used. It has been noted that additional research on fatigue analysis in the context of trailer design would help in designing a lighter chassis [1]. There are no fixed values for maximum allowable deflection, except for the load case of being parked and resting on the landing legs, where the maximum allowable deflection at the front end of the trailer is 50 mm. With regard to torsional stiffness, how much the chassis twists in service varies a great deal due to its make-up and operating conditions. As an approximate criterion, SDC Trailers typically apply a torsional load to cause the chassis to twist by 150 mm (vertical measurement between front and rear diagonal corners) and examine the resulting stress. Because industrial partners have indicated that torsion is far less critical than the other two cases and that it is specific to operating conditions, it has been neglected in this analysis.

In the linear elastic FE analysis, a displacement contour and stress plot was created for the critical static load case. The results of the modelling are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. It can be seen that the deflection of the chassis is 50 mm at the front end of the trailer and 2 mm at the rear of the trailer. In this load case, the maximum stress in the main longitudinal beams occurs at the goose-neck in the bottom flange and is approximately 40% of the yield stress, hence within the factor of safety i.e. 50% of the yield stress.

Figure 2: Displacement contour for the load case of resting on landing legs and trailer bogie (30 tonne UDL). U2 = displacement in the y-direction in millimetres.

Figure 3. Variation in stress in the trailer main beam from the rear (0 m) to the front end (13.5 m) for the load case of resting on landing legs and trailer bogie (30 tonne UDL).

3 OPTIMISATION METHODOLOGY

Since the trailer chassis it is a relatively complex shape, it demands a complicated structural analysis, such as FE analysis. Monroy Aceves et al. [2] developed a methodology for use in the design of composite structures by combining FE analysis with a graphical optimisation step, as shown in Fig. 4. The design problem specification step is used to define the limits on geometry and potential material combinations. A corresponding set of FE analysis input files were generated using Python. These were then submitted to the solver of FE software Abaqus, and results can then be extracted into a database. This was then read in MATLAB and performance maps can be generated which allow for design constraints to be applied. These help identify optimal solutions within the allowable design space. While this approach is computationally expensive as it requires many calculations and iterations, it is an effective way of filling out the design space and identifying optimal solutions within the conflicting design constraints. Indeed, advances in desktop computing power make this form of ‘brute-force’ analysis more feasible for use.

The methodology of Monroy Aceves et al. was applied here to examine in more detail the potential beam geometries and material combinations suited to a wholly composite trailer. In all scenarios investigated, the critical load case of the trailer resting on its landing legs and bogie was examined. The material properties used throughout the FE analysis are provided in Table 1. These materials were selected to give a broad scope in terms of mechanical properties (in particular stiffness), weight and raw material cost.

Material	E_1 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	σ_{1u} (MPa)	τ_{12u} (MPa)	ρ (kg/m ³)	Cost (£/kg)
Steel (YS355)	200	80	355	210	7,800	0.35
Aluminium	72	27	280	210	2,700	1.4
GFRP	23	3	860	83	1,800	1.2
CFRP	130	6	1,300	62	1,550	24

Table 1: Material properties used in finite element modelling [3].

Figure 4: Design methodology flowchart, adapted from Monroy Aceves et al. [2].

To give an indicator of mechanical performance, front and rear beam displacement, as well as failure index within the 13.5 m longitudinal beam, were all reported. The Tsai-Hill failure criterion (Eqn. 1) was applied to the 13.5 m longitudinal I-beam to determine the failure index. Because the FE models each use beam elements to model the longitudinal I-beams, the contributions of stress in the transverse 2-direction along the beam were neglected ($\sigma_2 = 0$), simplifying the full Tsai-Hill failure criterion from Eqn. 1 to Eqn. 2. The failure index can then be written as a percentage (Eqn. 3). This failure index is applied to all materials to simplify the automation of the analysis. Since the design of the beam is stiffness-driven, the choice of failure criterion does not impact on the final result of the optimisation procedure. However, it should be noted that the von Mises or Tresca yield criteria would be more appropriate for use with metals.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1u}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_{2u}}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_1\sigma_2}{\sigma_{1u}^2} + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12u}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1u}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12u}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$FI(\%) = \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1u}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12u}}\right)^2 \right] \times 100 \quad (3)$$

4 INFLUENCE OF TRAILER DECKING ON STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES

The optimisation of the longitudinal I-beams can be expanded to include other materials and combined with a structural decking that removes the need for the transverse members in the conventional ladder-type chassis structure. The resulting structure resembles a stiffened panel as shown in Fig. 5. Indeed, such a structure lends itself well to the application of composite materials and could also bring significant aerodynamic improvements. This structure was again modelled in Abaqus to investigate the performance of different materials for use in the deck and beams. The different materials and geometries considered for use in the longitudinal I-beams for this scenario are shown in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Two decks, differing by an order of magnitude in stiffness, were modelled to illustrate the broad potential of what could be achieved with a structural deck. The I-beam sections were once again modelled with beam elements, while the deck was modelled with a general shell section (with a simplified stiffness matrix $[D]$), that is perfectly connected to the top flanges of the beams. A 30 tonne UDL was applied to the top surface of the deck and the critical load case of the trailer resting on its landing legs and bogie was again examined (Fig. 1). The meshing of the model is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 5: Parameters of the FE model of the composite trailer. I-beams modelled with beam elements and deck modelled with a general shell section with a simplified stiffness matrix $[D]$. A 30 tonne UDL was applied to the top surface of the deck. Note that the x, z and y directions indicated correspond to the 1, 2 and 3 material directions, respectively.

Beam component	Modelled dimensions (mm)
Flange thickness	5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60
Flange width	100, 150, 200, 250, 350, 400
Web thickness	$2/3 \times$ flange thickness
Beam height – rear	385, 425, 465
Beam height – front	130, 150
Beam height – goose-neck	279

Table 2: Dimensions of the beams (5,184 geometry variations total) investigated with the two different structural decks of stiffness $[\mathbf{D}]_1$ and $[\mathbf{D}]_2$. Flange width and thickness remains uniform along the length of the beam.

Figure 6: Meshing of the FE model in Abaqus, with a typical mesh size of 10 cm, corresponding to 135 beam elements per beam and 3,375 shell elements for the decking.

The linear elastic response of the deck shell section is governed by Eqn. 4, which can be expanded to Eqn. 5. The 1, 2 and 3 directions in these equations correspond to the x , z and y directions, respectively, as shown in Fig. 5. In these equations, the direct membrane terms come first, then the shear membrane term, then the direct and shear bending terms, with six terms in all. Note that engineering measures of shear membrane strain (γ_{12}) and twist (κ_{12}) are used in Abaqus.

$$\{\mathbf{N}\} = [\mathbf{D}]\{\mathbf{E}\} \quad (4)$$

where

$\{\mathbf{N}\}$ are the membrane forces per unit length and bending moments per unit length;

$\{\mathbf{E}\}$ are the generalised section strains in the shell, and;

$[\mathbf{D}]$ is the section stiffness matrix.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_{11} \\ N_{22} \\ N_{12} \\ M_{11} \\ M_{22} \\ M_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{13} & D_{14} & D_{15} & D_{16} \\ D_{21} & D_{22} & D_{23} & D_{24} & D_{25} & D_{26} \\ D_{31} & D_{32} & D_{33} & D_{34} & D_{35} & D_{36} \\ D_{41} & D_{42} & D_{43} & D_{44} & D_{45} & D_{46} \\ D_{51} & D_{52} & D_{53} & D_{54} & D_{55} & D_{56} \\ D_{61} & D_{62} & D_{63} & D_{64} & D_{65} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \kappa_{11} \\ \kappa_{22} \\ \kappa_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The terms of the stiffness matrices for the two different structural decks are defined in Eqns. 6 and 7. The stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{D}]_1$ is representative of a pultruded GFRP decking. It was assumed the mass of this deck is 440 kg. The stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{D}]_2$ is representative of quasi-isotropic CFRP-balsa

sandwich panel with 5 mm thick face sheets and a 50 mm thick core. The total mass of this deck was calculated to be approximately 910 kg. Note that this deck is an order of magnitude stiffer than the pultruded GFRP decking, and represents an upper limit of stiffness that could be achieved in practical terms using a lightweight structural deck.

$$[\mathbf{D}]_1 : D_{22} = 1.7 \times 10^5 \text{ N/mm}, D_{55} = 3.2 \times 10^5 \text{ Nmm}, D_{11} = D_{33} = D_{44} = D_{66} \approx 0 \quad (6)$$

$$[\mathbf{D}]_2 : D_{11} = D_{22} = 1.0 \times 10^6 \text{ N/mm}, D_{44} = D_{55} = 3.0 \times 10^8 \text{ Nmm}, D_{33} = D_{66} \approx 0 \quad (7)$$

The results of the modelling procedure for the most critical design constraint, the front-end displacement of the beams, are shown in Fig. 7. It is evident when comparing Fig. 7a and 7b, that the significantly stiffer decking did not significantly increase the mechanical performance of the structure. This is evident in Fig. 7b where the solution clouds have shifted rightwards on the graph in comparison to Fig. 7a, without having shifted downward enough to include solutions with GFRP-based beams, which could bring a substantial cost benefit. This shows that the stiffer decking added a significant amount of weight (approximately 500 kg) to the structure. A CFRP-based decking would also be considerably more expensive than a GFRP based decking, reiterating that a lighter, less stiff decking seems to be a more sensible choice. It is also evident from Fig. 7 that CFRP beams are the best material choice for lightweight, high performance beams. This is demonstrated through the fact that models with CFRP beams are the most prominent solutions to feature in the light and stiff design envelopes depicted by the boxes in the bottom left quadrants of the graphs. Indeed, CFRP composite beams could work well in conjunction with a composite decking, with single shot manufacturing options being a possibility in the future. Composite beams are explored in greater detail in the following section.

Figure 7: Displacement of the main longitudinal I-beams (made of different materials indicated by different marker colours) at the front end for a 30 tonne UDL, plotted against total chassis mass (combined mass of the beams and decking).

(a) Deck shell stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{D}]_1$: Pultruded GFRP decking (440 kg).

(b) Deck shell stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{D}]_2$: CFRP-balsa sandwich panel decking (910 kg).

Note that the total mass of the corresponding current typical steel chassis and hardwood decking is approximately 2,000 kg.

5 OPTIMISATION OF LIGHTWEIGHT COMPOSITE CHASSIS

Having identified GFRP-based structural decking to be the most advantageous in terms of weight, cost and mechanical performance, additional modelling was performed to examine in more detail a composite beam design for use in conjunction with this type of decking. It was evident from the previous section that CFRP beams are the most advantageous in terms of balancing weight reduction and mechanical performance. However, their significantly higher raw material cost needs to be taken into consideration. To this end, additional hypothetical Glass-Carbon beams were modelled, whereby the rear of the beam is modelled as GFRP, while the front end of the beam was modelled as CFRP. This strategy was used to reduce weight while keeping raw material cost increase to a minimum, and maintaining mechanical performance. This kind of mixed Glass-Carbon structure could be difficult and costly to achieve with current composite manufacturing technologies. However it may become more feasible with future advancements.

The geometries considered for use in the I-longitudinal beams in this modelling are shown in Table 3, while the beam material properties are defined in Table 1. The deck is defined by the shell stiffness matrix $[D]_1$. The deck was assumed to have a mass of 440 kg.

Beam component	Modelled dimensions (mm)
Rear flange thickness (t_r)	2.5, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15
Front and goose-neck flange thickness (t_{fr})	5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30
Rear flange width	150, 250, 350, 450, 550, 650, 750, 850, 950, 1050, 1150, 1250
Front and goose-neck flange width	150, 250, 350, 450, 550, 650, 750, 850, 950, 1050, 1150, 1250
Rear web thickness	$2/3 \times t_r$
Front and goose-neck web thickness	$2/3 \times t_{fr}$

Table 3: Dimensions of the lightweight composite beams (5,184 total geometry variations) modelled in conjunction with the structural decking defined by the simplified stiffness matrix $[D]_1$.

The results of the modelling and optimisation of the composite chassis are presented in Figs. 8 and Table 4, respectively. The current stiffness requirements (assumed to be 50 mm and 2 mm of deflection at the front and rear end, respectively) are plotted as horizontal lines in Fig. 8a and 8b. It is evident in Fig. 8 that the shape-optimised CFRP beams combined with GFRP decking (model A) could reduce the overall chassis mass by approximately 60% (1207 kg), while meeting the current design constraints for stiffness and strength. On the other hand, at the current conventional design constraints, the shape-optimised Glass-Carbon beams with GFRP decking (model B) could only reduce overall chassis mass by approximately 19% (370 kg) and would have significantly larger dimensions, as shown in Table 4. However, assuming that the maximum allowable rear end displacement could be relaxed from 2 mm to 4 mm (as shown in Fig. 8b), shape-optimised Glass-Carbon beams (model B1) become significantly more attractive, as their weight-saving potential rises from 19% to 47% (940 kg). By restricting the use of CFRP to the front end only, the overall raw material cost associated with the chassis becomes significantly lower than in the case when CFRP is used in the entire beam (Fig. 6.13d). The largest weight reduction potential was observed in the chassis with shape-optimised CFRP beams with an allowable rear displacement of 4 mm (model A1), as shown in Fig. 8. In this case, weight is reduced by approximately 66% (1326 kg).

Figure 8: Performance plots of the composites chassis modelled in Abaqus with a 30 tonne Uniformly Distributed Load applied to the top surface of the decking. (a) Displacement of the main longitudinal beam at the front end. (b) Displacement of the main longitudinal beam at the rear end. (c) Maximum failure index within the beam. (d) Total raw material cost. Notes: All models use pultruded GFRP decking (440 kg). Red markers indicate CFRP beams and blue markers indicate GFRP at the rear of the two main longitudinal beams and CFRP at the front end of the beams. Further details of models A, A1, B, and B1 are provided in Table 4. Current allowable displacement at the rear of the beam is 2 mm, this could potentially be relaxed to 4 mm to further increase weight savings.

Model	Rear beam material	Rear flange width (mm)	Front beam material	Front flange width (mm)	Total mass (kg)	Weight saving (%)
A	Carbon fibre	450	Carbon fibre	650	793	60
A1	Carbon fibre	150	Carbon fibre	750	674	66
B	Glass fibre	1,150	Carbon fibre	650	1,630	19
B1	Glass fibre	850	Carbon fibre	850	1,060	47

Table 4: Key features of optimised composite trailer chassis with pultruded glass fibre decking.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The current conventional 13.5 m steel ladder-type trailer chassis has been refined over time through experience. There are undoubtedly improvements that could be made to the existing structure through a greater understanding of in-service loadings. A better understanding of in-service loadings could be combined well with the FE modelling and steel beam optimisation procedures introduced here to reduce chassis weight even further. More significant weight reductions are more likely to be realised through a wholly composite chassis. While the stiffened panel composite trailer structures presented could be difficult and costly to produce with current composite manufacturing technologies, it may become increasingly feasible with advancements in processing techniques such as pultruding. A composite chassis comprised of CFRP beams and a pultruded GFRP deck could reduce overall trailer weight by up to 1326 kg (67%). However, the high material costs associated with CFRP could dictate that a more desirable approach could be to use CFRP in the front end of the beams and GFRP in the rear end of the beams. FE modelling and optimisation has shown that this structure would reduce trailer weight by approximately 940 kg (47%). It is also clear that reducing the maximum allowable rear end displacement from 2 mm to 4 mm would allow for the most significant levels of weight reduction to be realised.

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